

STUDIES ON ADSORPTION IN RELATION TO CONSTITUTION. PART I. ADSORPTION OF ALKALOIDS BY SILICA GEL.

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Adsorption of a number of alkaloids from alcoholic solutions on silica gel has been studied. Considerable amounts of the alkaloids are adsorbed and the adsorption process follows Freundlich's equation. The attainment of equilibrium has been found to be a slow process. The temperature coefficients of adsorption are generally large. Similarly constituted alkaloids have given comparable adsorption coefficients. A parallelism between physiological activity and adsorption is also observed.

The adsorption of individual alkaloids on different surfaces has frequently been observed. Thus Moravek (*Ark. Kem. Min. Geol.*, 1923, 8, No. 30, 1), found that brucine dissolved in benzene or toluene was strongly adsorbed on fused *d*-tartaric acid; the amount adsorbed was ten times as large as that required for the formation of a monomolecular layer. Graham and Carr (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 695) reported that nicotine compounds of calcium were present in tobacco grown on soil rich in lime. This apparent union of calcium and nicotine was explained by Chapin (*ibid.*, 1925, 47, 892) as an adsorption process. This view was confirmed by Thatcher's (*ibid.*, 1924, 46, 1539) observation that nicotine was completely removed when shaken with calcium carbonate. Sartorius and Ottemeyer (*Z. unters. Lebensm.*, 1929, 88, 353) compared the adsorptive capacity of various brands of powdered and granular charcoal for caffeine. Most of the caffeine was adsorbed from solution immediately; on longer contact the adsorption curve reached a maximum which later on followed a slight decline. Rise of temperature accelerated the adsorption but decreased the quantity. The adsorption from coffee infusions was less than from pure caffeine solutions; the colour and aroma of the infusions were not perceptibly affected by the process. The adsorption of quinine on active charcoal (morit) was studied by Guerrant and Salmon (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, 80, 67). The p_{H} of the solution considerably modified the adsorption of quinine hydrogen sulphate. Malquori (*Anal. Chim. Appl.*, 1932, 22, 448) studied the adsorption of the hydrochlorides of nicotine, caffeine and quinine on silica gel and on the hydroxides of aluminium, chromium and iron. The adsorption in each case was found to be considerable. Silica gel was found to be much more active towards the nicotine salt than towards quinine hydrochloride. Hydrolytic adsorption of the latter was not observed.

From the examples stated above, it is evident that the adsorption of alkaloids vary considerably both in the nature and extent of the process. A detailed study of the adsorption of alkaloids on silica gel has been undertaken in the present investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The adsorption of morphine, nicotine, strychnine, brucine, quinidine, cinchonidine, quinine, piperine and caffeine from alcoholic solutions has been determined. The solutions used were of comparable concentrations and contained 0.5 g. of the pure alkaloid in 100 c.c. of absolute alcohol, except in the case of strychnine of which a saturated solution was used. Usually 25 c.c. of the solutions were shaken with 2 to 5 g. of silica gel in well stoppered bottles and left for a sufficiently long time to attain equilibrium. The amount of adsorption was determined by analysis before and after the addition of the gel. The gel used in these experiments was a sample obtained from the Silica Gel Corporation. To activate the gel it was first washed with distilled water for several days till free from acid and then dried at 100°. The gel was next heated to about 300° and a current of carbon dioxide-free air was drawn through it for three hours. The gel activated in this way was stored in a desiccator.

Estimation of alkaloids, specially when present in mixtures is a matter of some difficulty. As pointed out by Prescott, estimation with Wagner's reagent or Meyer's reagent is not reliable as the composition of the precipitated iodides depends on concentration, temperature, time and other factors (cf. *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2871; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1900, 39, 201; Hezzig, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1922, 259, 249). In the present investigation, however, estimation of only single alkaloid is required. Direct titration against standard acid with a properly selected indicator has been found to be sufficiently accurate. The suitability of different indicators in the titrations of alkaloids has been considered by McGill (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 2156). In a number of cases the alkaloid solutions were also analysed by conductometric titration with silicotungstic acid (Lamberst and Foster, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1932, A, 134, 246). The two sets of data agreed within 1 to 1.5%. Estimation by silicotungstic acid, though accurate, has certain drawbacks. The crystals easily lose water of crystallisation and need recrystallisation before use. Further, the solution has to be standardised before each determination. Estimation by direct titration with suitable indicators, was, therefore, found more convenient and has been generally used in the present experiments. The estimations of caffeine and piperine solutions were carried out by careful evaporation and direct weighing.

Preliminary experiments showed that 90% of the adsorption took place rapidly within the first 24 hours. After this the system continued to change very slowly and complete equilibrium was not established even after several weeks. To determine the exact equilibrium time, 100 c.c. each of 7 alkaloid solutions were kept in well stoppered bottles with 5 g. of gel and changes in the concentrations of the alkaloid solutions were followed over a period of 75 days. The results are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Rate of adsorption of alkaloids by silica gel.

No. of days.	Changes in concentration titre against N/100 HCl.								
	0	3	6	10	15	20	40	60	70
Morphine	7.70	6.20	5.90	5.70	5.40	5.30	5.30	—	—
Nicotine	13.70	10.90	10.90	—	—	—	—	—	—
Quinine	6.95	6.00	5.70	5.60	5.50	5.40	5.40	—	—
Quinidine	7.55	6.35	6.05	5.90	5.85	5.80	5.80	—	—
Cinchonidine	8.15	6.85	6.75	6.60	6.50	6.40	5.40	—	—
Brucine	5.20	3.60	3.30	3.00	2.80	2.60	2.30	2.10	2.10
Strychnine	4.10	2.40	2.10	1.90	1.75	1.70	1.60	1.60	—

From Table I complete equilibrium appears to be established in most cases only after 20 days, except in the case of nicotine where equilibrium was established within 3 days.

Adsorption from solutions is generally considered to be rapid, equilibrium being established in a few hours or a few days. In the case of brucine in the present experiments, the equilibrium was not complete till after 60 days. Such a long equilibrium time raises the question as to whether the changes in the titration values are really due to slow attainment of equilibrium or are due to some slow chemical change occurring in the system. It is well known that alcohol undergoes dehydration or oxidation in the vapour phase in presence of a proper catalyst. If silica gel were playing a similar role, alcohol, even in the liquid phase, on prolonged contact with the gel, might undergo chemical changes. To test the point a blank experiment was performed. After standing in contact with the gel for about two weeks, the alcohol gave no tests for either ethylene or aldehydes, but had developed minute traces of acid. The possibility of any chemical change in the alcohol itself thus seems remote. One must, therefore, conclude that the attainment of equilibrium in these adsorption experiments is really an extremely slow process.

A set of adsorption values for alcoholic solutions of different alkaloids is given in Table II.

TABLE II.

25 C.c. of solution treated with 5 g. of gel in each case.

Alkaloid.	Initial conc. (g./100 c.c.).	Initial titre (c.c.).	Final titre (c.c.).	Adsorption.	Alkaloid.	Initial conc. (g./100 c.c.).	Initial titre (c.c.).	Final titre (c.c.).	Adsorption.
Morphine	0.5 g.	23.7	8.4	63.7%	Cinchonidine	0.5 g	25.0	9.2	63.2%
Nicotine	..	42.0	19.0	78.5	Brucine	..	16.0	2.7	83.1
Quinine	..	21.2	10.8	49.0	Strychnine	0.4	14.0	1.3	80.6
Quinidine	..	23.3	8.9	61.8	Caffeine.	0.25	—	—	20.8
					Piperine	0.25	—	—	2.4

Table II indicates that positive adsorption is obtained in every case except in that of piperine, where the solution after treatment with the gel was slightly more concentrated and thus established negative adsorption. As is well known silica gel can adsorb considerable quantities of alcohol vapour (cf. Lambert and Foster, at saturation 0.218 c.c. of alcohol are adsorbed per g. of the gel). If the same amount of alcohol be removed by preferential adsorption by silica gel from the alcoholic solution of piperine, it would introduce an increase in concentration of 3.8%. This is of the same order as actually found with the piperine solution. The observed negative adsorption is, therefore, simply due to the preferential adsorption of the alcohol from the solution. That piperine itself is not adsorbed was also found by washing the gel free from adhering solution and then treating the dry gel with concentrated acid when no colour or stain was developed. Incidentally it might be mentioned that the same amount of alcohol must be preferentially adsorbed by the gel in the case of the other alkaloid solutions also. The amount, however, is small and would not materially alter the amounts of adsorption.

To study the effect of concentration on the adsorption process, adsorption isotherms have been determined and the results are given in the following tables. The concentration terms in the tables refer to the amounts in g. mols present in 25 c.c. of the solution. x/m represents the number of mols ($\times 10^3$) of alkaloid adsorbed per g. of gel.

TABLE III.

25 C.c. of morphine solution treated with 4 g. of gel.

Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed	x/m .	$\log C$.	$\log x/m$.
8.77×10^{-5}	2.04×10^{-5}	6.73×10^{-5}	1.68	0.3096	0.2253
17.54	6.12	11.42	2.86	0.7868	0.4564
26.31	11.42	14.89	3.72	1.0577	0.5705
35.08	16.52	18.56	4.64	1.2186	0.6665
43.85	22.23	21.62	5.41	1.3470	0.7332

TABLE IV.

25 C.c. of nicotine solution treated with 3 g. of gel.

Initial conc	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed	x/m .	$\log C$.	$\log x/m$.
15.43×10^{-5}	5.43×10^{-5}	10.00×10^{-5}	3.33	0.7340	0.5224
30.86	12.01	18.85	6.28	1.0795	0.7980
46.29	19.41	26.88	8.96	1.2880	0.9523
61.72	26.65	35.07	11.69	1.4257	1.0679
77.15	34.38	42.77	14.26	1.5363	1.1541

TABLE V.

25 C.c. of quinine solution treated with 5 g. of gel.

Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	x/m .	$\log C$.	$\log x/m$.
6.61×10^{-5}	2.55×10^{-5}	4.06×10^{-5}	0.82	0.4065	-0.0862
13.22	5.70	7.52	1.50	0.7559	0.1761
19.83	9.30	10.53	2.11	0.9585	0.3243
26.44	12.90	13.54	2.71	1.1106	0.4330
33.05	16.80	16.25	3.25	1.2253	0.5119

TABLE VI.

25 C.c. of quinine solution treated with 3 g. of gel.

Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	x/m .	$\log C$.	$\log x/m$.
7.72×10^{-5}	4.75×10^{-5}	2.97×10^{-5}	0.99	0.6767	-0.0004
15.43	9.84	5.59	1.86	0.9930	0.2695
23.15	14.76	8.39	2.80	1.1690	0.4472
30.86	19.68	11.18	3.73	1.2940	0.5717
38.58	24.92	13.66	4.55	1.3966	0.6580

TABLE VII.

25 C.c. of cinchonidine solution treated with 3 g. of gel.

Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	x/m .	$\log C$.	$\log x/m$.
8.52×10^{-5}	4.84×10^{-5}	3.68×10^{-5}	1.23	0.6848	0.0899
17.04	9.85	7.19	2.42	0.9914	0.3800
25.56	15.03	10.53	3.51	1.1769	0.5433
34.08	20.54	13.54	4.51	1.3126	0.6542
42.60	26.22	16.38	5.46	1.4186	0.7372

TABLE VIII.

25 C.c. of brucine solution treated with 5 g. of gel.

Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	x/m .	$\log C$.	$\log x/m$.
5.36×10^{-5}	0.57×10^{-5}	4.79×10^{-5}	0.96	-0.2441	-0.0177
10.73	1.32	9.41	1.88	0.1206	0.2742
16.09	2.30	13.79	2.76	0.3607	0.4404
21.46	3.23	18.23	3.65	0.5092	0.5623
26.82	4.56	22.26	4.45	0.6590	0.6424

TABLE IX.

25 C.c. of strychnine solution treated with 5 g. of gel.

Initial conc.	Equil. conc.	Amount adsorbed.	x/m	$\log C$.	$\log x/m$.
6.00×10^{-5}	0.429×10^{-5}	5.57×10^{-5}	1.11	-0.3675	0.0453
12.00	1.144	10.86	2.17	0.0584	0.3365
18.00	2.002	16.00	3.20	0.3014	0.5031
24.00	2.860	21.14	4.30	0.4564	0.6335
30.00	3.718	26.28	5.26	0.5705	0.7210

The adsorption isotherms are shown in Fig. 1. The amount of adsorption has been reckoned in terms of g.mols of the alkaloid per. g. of the gel. The concentration values used in plotting the isotherms represent equilibrium concentrations. As will be seen from the figure, the plot of $\log x/m$ against $\log C$ is generally a straight line. The adsorption of the alkaloids thus follows the Freundlich adsorption equation.

An examination of the figure further shows that the adsorption isotherms for brucine and strychnine run parallel and close to one another. These

FIG. 1.

two alkaloids are similar in constitution and differ from one another in respect of two methoxy groups only. So far as this pair of alkaloids is concerned, it would appear that compounds similar in constitution have comparable adsorption. A parallelism between constitution and adsorption is also seen in the case of the cinchona alkaloids. The adsorption isotherms of cinchonidine, quinidine and quinine form a cluster which are close to one another. The isotherms of quinidine and cinchonidine are parallel to one another, the values for quinine lying practically intermediate between these isotherms. Bearing in mind the fact that the cinchona alkaloids are difficult to obtain in an absolutely pure state, the three adsorption isotherms may be considered and sufficiently close to one another to justify the conclusion that compounds allied in constitution have similar adsorption.

A comparison of the tables given above shows that brucine, strychnine and nicotine are adsorbed the most from solutions. It is interesting to note that in respect of physiological action, the above three are the most poisonous amongst all the alkaloids studied in these experiments. Morphine has shown a distinctly lower adsorption. Its pharmacopoeic dose is between 6.39 mg. compared to 1.4 mg. for strychnine. Piperine which has no positive adsorption at all is not ordinarily a poison. There is thus a definite indication that the alkaloids which act physiologically as powerful poisons are very largely adsorbed. The point, however, should not be stretched too far for obvious reasons.

TABLE X.

Alkaloid.	Initial titre.	Final titre.				$\left(\frac{x/m \text{ at } 45^\circ}{x/m \text{ at } 35^\circ}\right)$	$\left(\frac{x/m \text{ at } 40^\circ}{x/m \text{ at } 30^\circ}\right)$
		30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.		
Nicotine	23.7	15.7	18.0	19.8	20.6	0.544	0.488
Quinine	13.9	9.1	10.5	11.3	11.8	0.618	0.542
Brucine	10.4	2.5	3.3	4.2	4.9	0.775	0.785
Morphine	15.4	8.0	9.1	10.2	11.1	0.683	0.703
Cinchonidine	16.7	10.4	10.9	11.6	12.0	0.825	0.809
Quinidine	15.0	10.1	10.7	11.4	12.0	0.669	0.325
Strychnine	8.4	1.9	2.4	3.0	3.6	0.800	0.831

The effect of temperature on the adsorption processes has also been studied. Experiments were performed at 30°, 35°, 40°, and 45° and the results are given in Table X.

The temperature coefficients are given in the last two columns of the table. As will be seen from the values a ten degree rise in temperature reduces the amount of adsorption by 30 to 50%.

Further experiments are in progress.

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